

D7.5 Communication tools V2

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5g-iana.eu

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Control sheet

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-IANA	5G for Intelligent Automotive Network Applications
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOEP	Automotive Open Experimentation Platform
API	Application Programming Interface
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MANO	Management and Orchestration
nApp	Network Application
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
VNF	Virtualised Network Function
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The design, implementation and management of communication tools and materials is part of Task 7.1 Communication strategy and tools. D7.4 - Communication tools, issued in M9, presented the communication tools, channels, and materials put in place by the 5G-IANA consortium as the main instruments for the correct performance of communication and dissemination actions. This deliverable, D7.5 - Communication tools V2, is an updated version of the document: it analyses the performance and impact achieved by the communication tools, channels, and materials defined in D7.4 and introduces the new elements required so as to adapt the communication tools to the needs of the project.

The deliverable consists of the following sections:

- Chapter 1 consists of an introduction to the 5G-IANA project's concept and approach, to the purpose of the deliverable and intended audience.
- Chapter 2 analyses the communication tools and channels put in place by the project.
- Chapter 3 presents the impact achieved by 5G-IANA communication tools during the period M1-M20.
- Chapter 4 is the conclusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., SMEs in the Automotive vertical sector will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. The provided Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) is a set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector, for simplifying the design and onboarding of new nApps. 5G-IANA exposes to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA targets different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of end-to-end network services across different segments (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA nApp toolkit is linked with an Automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extensive portfolio of ready-to-use and openly accessible Automotive-related VNFs and nApp templates, that are available for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA develops a Distributed Machine Learning (DML) framework, that provides functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of Machine Learning (ML) service components and thus, allows ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy-preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven Automotive-related use cases in two 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models for the AOEP platform, supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as a key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable D7.5 – Communication tools v2 belongs to the set of WP7 deliverables, and it is directly linked to Task 7.1 Communication strategy and tools. The document provides an overview of the communication tools put in place by the 5G-IANA

consortium for the correct performance of communication activities as well as the impact achieved up to M20.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of this document is “public” (PU) and is primarily aimed at the consortium members and the European Commission. However, any interested actor is able to download it and read it.

2. COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS

2.1. Brand identity and logo

Brand and visual identity represent the first contact the public has with our project. Conceived as the project's initial communication tool, 5G-IANA brand and visual identity use a set of graphic elements to easily identify the 5G-IANA project. Deliverable 7.1 – 'Brand Identity and guidelines' collects and presents how the project aims - through the logos, the brand identity, and other graphic files - to create a coherent, consistent, and highly recognisable image of the project that supports communication and dissemination activities, aiming to enable and to maintain the integrity of the project's overall brand identity to ensure efficient communication of the project and its results (Figure 1).

Figure 1, 5G-IANA logo

A set of templates has been also created to ensure homogeneity and consistency on presentations and deliverable releases. More specifically 5G-IANA prepared the following:

- a presentation template to be used by all partners when presenting the project;
- a deliverable template for submitting the project's deliverables;
- agenda and minutes templates for project events and meetings.

2.2. Website

5G-IANA's official website domain is: <https://www.5g-iana.eu/>. As already stated in D7.4, the aim of the website is to promote the 5G-IANA project, its objectives and achievements. It serves as the main communication channel, containing all the necessary information of the project and being constantly updated with the latest developments. The website will also be the main vehicle for advertising and encouraging third-parties to participate at the project's two Open Calls during the second half of the project.

In order to ensure that the project reflects the project's progress, T7.1 has been regularly revising and updating the website's structure and content and, in cross-collaboration with WP6, has developed a new section specifically dedicated to the engagement of third-party experimenters to the Open Calls.

2.2.1. Website update

An update of the website was addressed during the second year of the project with the aim of improving the [level of technical information](#) provided (the 5G-IANA AOEP platform, the Network Applications, the architecture, and the Use Cases) and for easing the access to the information (the content on the [News](#) and the [Resources](#) section have been enhanced and re-organised).

The updates addressed, section by section, are summarized below:

2.2.1.1. Homepage

The summary of the project in the [homepage](#) (Figure 2) has been revisited, replacing the objectives of the project (that are now presented on a dedicated page in the About section) with the general scope of the project. The first introductory video of the project has been added in the homepage allowing a very easy access to the scope and summary of the project.

Figure 2, 5G-IANA website homepage

2.2.1.2. About

The [About](#) section (Figure 3) has been extended and the information is now re-organised under six sub-sections:

- **Concept and approach:** this section summarises the context behind the project and presents the 5G-IANA Concept & Approach, the architecture of the AOEP, and the Network Applications (nApps).
- **Objectives:** this section provides the detailed objectives of the project.
- **Use Cases:** this new subsection presents the seven Use Cases defined by the project to demonstrate and validate the 5G-IANA platform.
- **Testbeds:** this section briefly presents the project’s two test sites. More details about these sites are available in the new section “Get Involved” described below.

- **Work Packages:** this section provides a short summary for each of the project’s Work Packages.
- **5G-PPP involvement:** this subpage gives a short description of the 5G-PPP initiative, the involvement of 5G-IANA in it, as well as a link to its website.

Figure 3, 5G-IANA “ABOUT” website section and sub-sections

2.2.1.3. Resources

As the amount of content continues to increase with the progress of the project (the number of publications, deliverables, newsletters, etc.) and new activities are coming up (webinars, videos, presentations, etc.), the [Resources](#) section was restructured to better organise the information and facilitate user navigation on the page.

A main menu (Figure 4) provides a direct and easy-to-navigate access to the following eight sub-pages that are currently available (four new have been created for webinars, videos, presentations, and press releases):

- **Webinars:** all webinar recordings will be uploaded here.

- **Papers and Publications:** all publications of the project are available on the website through their Zenodo link to the project’s Community where they are openly-accessible.
- **Newsletters:** 5G-IANA Newsletter issues are announced on the website with a link to the project’s Zenodo Community where they are published.
- **Deliverables:** this section has been also re-organised, and deliverables are now presented per Work Package.
- **Videos:** all videos of the project will be available in this section. The first video of the project has been already published.
- **Communication materials:** this section contains the materials already developed by the project (the logo, the flyer, the poster, the brochure, and the roll-up banner). All new materials will be provided here.
- **Presentations** of the project are provided in this section.
- **Press releases** are published on this section.

Figure 4, 5G-IANA “RESOURCES” website section and sub-sections

2.2.1.4. News

The [News](#) section (Figure 5) has been also re-organised under three sub-sections to facilitate the follow-up of the activities and key events of the project.

- **Project News:** includes announcements of all past and future project activities (participation at events, new publications, new resources available, etc).
- **Technical Blog:** contains blog-style articles of technical content, addressed to the general audience and authored by the partners of the consortium.
- **Events:** presents the upcoming events that the project endorses or will actively participate at.

Figure 5, 5G-IANA “NEWS” website section

2.2.2. New website section for engagement of third parties: “[Get Involved](#)”

This new menu has been created in February 2023, in cross-collaboration with WP6 and the project coordinator, to guide external experimenters through engaging with the 5G-IANA open experimentation platform, especially during the project’s two Open Calls (Figure 6). The first release of this section has the following three sub-menus; however, the information provided will be constantly updated on the needs of the different Open Call phases:

- **5G-IANA third-party experimentation:** summarises the objectives of the project in relation to the involvement of SMEs, offers a detailed summary of the 5G-IANA platform capabilities, and presents the testbed facilities that the project makes available to experimenters.
- **5G-IANA Open Call #1:** this page provides the scope and terms of the Open Call together with the instructions to participate (who, when and how to apply). The application form to formalise the participation is also available in this section. The “Guide for Applicants”, the core document of this Open Call, contains the detailed Open Call conditions and is available for download in this section.
- **Mentors:** close mentorship and support will be provided to the selected experimenters so that they get familiarised with the platform. This section aims to introduce to potential applicants the people exercising this role during the first Open Call.

5G-IANA Open Call #1

5G-IANA project is calling for SMEs and start-ups from Europe to apply to our first Open Call that will allow them to run their automotive network applications on top of the platform provided by the 5G-IANA project making use of 5G connectivity. The 5G-IANA consortium will support its participants to develop and integrate their innovative ideas using the 5G-IANA platform, facilitating in parallel the developed Repository of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs)

Selected participants will reap the following benefits offered by 5G-IANA:

- Gain access to a “canvas” to develop new functions and services in the automotive 5G landscape.
- Test and validate their existing or new services in real-time with 5G connectivity.
- Gain access to real-life 5G resources (vehicles, OBU, RSUs, edge server/MEC).
- Get continuous mentorship and support from network and automotive experts.
- Explore/build new business models within the 5G ecosystem.
- Gain visibility towards the EU, the 5G community and automotive community.

The program will last for 5 months, starting in June 2023.
Applications are open until 22nd May 2023 05:00:00 PM CEST.

[APPLY HERE](#)

User Guidelines full document
Download as a PDF document

What we offer?

SG-IANA offers to interested stakeholders:

- Access to the "AOEP" platform to develop, deploy and test their services.
- A catalogue of available virtual application and network functions (AFs/NFs, approx. 70), and Network Applications (nApps) (approx. 26).
- Tools to prepare and onboard their own AFs, NFs or nApps on the SG-IANA platform.
- Indicative examples and experience regarding the actual deployment of use cases of the SG-IANA consortium (into the platform, i.e. automotive related services in the hazard notification, infotainment, vehicle movement or even vertical-agnostic domain).
- Remote accessibility to 5G resources (through NOKIA's site in the City of Ulm, Germany / Telecom Slovenia's site in Ljubljana).
- Accessibility to OBU/RSU resources through the AOEP platform and experimentation potential using real vehicles.
- Support to Machine Learning (ML)-oriented services.
- Technical support material in the form of a technical manual, webinars and other published material.
- Mentorship, training, technical assistance and support.
- Business model mentoring.
- Access to SG-IANA project's network of entrepreneurs, professionals, media, and partners.
- Four monetary awards to the best performing experimenters in the order of 10-15K euros.

Who can apply?

The call is addressed to Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME) / start-ups working with the concept of Network Applications (nApps) in the automotive vertical and which are already developing or willing to develop a product or service that leverages 5G capabilities through the SG-IANA platform.

When to apply?

The program starts in June 2023 and ends in October 2023.

Applications are already open!

Application period: 22nd February-22nd May 2023
Evaluation period: 22nd May-31st May 2023
Pre testing phase: June-July 2023
Validation & testing phase: July-October 2023
Reporting period: November 2023
Award phase: December 2023

How to apply?

Application Submission **Deadline is 22nd May 2023 05:00:00 PM CEST!**

The Open Call Interest Form is available here for applying*

*For more information about the procedures for the submission of applications please refer to Section 3 of the "Guide for Applicants: How to Apply".

User Guidelines full document
Download as a PDF document

5G-IANA Open Call Interest Form

Step 1 General Information ↓

Step 2 Ambitions and development plans ↓

Step 3 Experience ↓

Step 4 Expectations from the platform ↓

Step 5 Expected impact ↓

Step 6 Before you submit ↓

All Open Call projects will be expected to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

[Send](#)

Need support?

Reach us at:
open-call@5g-iana.eu

Figure 6, 5G-IANA “Open Call #1” website section

2.2.3. Website statistics

The total visits to the 5G-IANA website are tracked through Google Analytics on a monthly basis. Figure 7 shows the number of visits per month to the 5G-IANA website since the 10th of November 2021 (when the website went live) until the 31st of January 2023 (M20). The average of website visitors per month during this period was 163.

Figure 7, 5G-IANA website total visits per month & articles published

This figure shows that the number of visitors was constant during the first year of the project, with an average of 100 visits per month. The number has increased during the second year of the project (average is 218 up to M20) and the trend seems to stabilise around this figure. The number of visits is expected to keep increasing in the short term with the new section “Get Involved “coming out.

Figure 7 also shows the number of News articles published on the website. The project is very active in communicating its progress and dissemination activities: at least one article is published every month although almost every month two articles are published.

Figure 8 presents the number of views by page title, while Figure 9 presents the average engagement time on the website. Finally, Figure 10 (landing page) shows that most of the web users land at the 5G-IANA webpage through the News and Resources section.

Figure 8, 5G-IANA website number of views by page title

Figure 9, 5G-IANA website average engagement time

Landing page: Landing page ✓		Custom		10 Nov 2021 - 31 Jan 2023	
3	/2022/03/02/local-dynamic-maps-ldm-for-cooperative-data-fusion	91	67	61	0m 45
4	/2022/11/28/5g-iana-plenary-meeting-23-24-november-2022	72	67	58	0m 09
5	/2022/04/26/ar-and-vr-for-in-vehicle-entertainment	58	55	54	0m 25
6	/2022/03/11/role-of-5g-networks-in-vehicle-to-infrastructure-telecommunications	43	41	39	0m 45
7	/2022/01/04/distributed-machine-learning-for-network-monitoring-and-predictive-qos-in-automotive-applications	26	19	16	0m 24
8	/resources	26	20	13	1m 05
9	/2022/07/18/5g-backed-situational-awareness-for-improved-road-tunnel-safety	21	20	20	1m 30

Figure 10, 5G-IANA website views by landing page

2.3. Social media

Social media accounts are being used to raise awareness of the project and to showcase and promote the 5G-IANA activities and events. An active update of the accounts aims as well to encourage a steady flow of traffic towards the 5G-IANA website to broaden the scope of the project’s activities and exploit connections with partners, other related projects, and their respective communication activities.

2.3.1. LinkedIn

The [5G-IANA LinkedIn](#) page is available since M01 of the project. Being the most popular social network among professionals, the added value of this tool remains on the opportunity of sharing project information across the professional world and a wide range of audiences.

The 5G-IANA LinkedIn account has gained 193 followers up until M20. Figure 11 below shows the trend of followers since the beginning of the project. In order to improve evaluation performance of this tool, T7.1 is now separately tracking between followers that are part of the Consortium (i.e., any individual member of the partners that constitute the Consortium) and members that do not have any link to the project’s partners. The

analysis proves that the number of followers outside the Consortium is clearly higher: 143 followers come from outside the Consortium up to M20. This figure also shows that the number of followers coming from Consortium partners is reducing as the project progresses (38 out of 104 on Y1 and 12 out of 89 during Y2). This number (users from the Consortium) seems to increase when the project has physical meetings (M13 mid-term review and M18 Plenary Meeting).

Figure 11, 5G-IANA LinkedIn group members

Figure 12 shows the number of posts on 5G-IANA LinkedIn account per month: on average, the project has posted 5 entries per month until M20.

Figure 12, Trend of 5G-IANA posts in LinkedIn

This constant activity is having a great impact on the visitor metrics too (the account had 522 visits in the last year) as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13, 5G-IANA LinkedIn visitor metrics

The analysis of the most recent 20 posts (Figure 14 and Figure 15) also shows that the engagement rate of LinkedIn posts is high.

Post title	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	CTR	Reactions	Comments	Reposts	Follows	Engagement rate
Count down for the launching of #SGIANA first Open Call #SGIANA will... Posted by Andrea Suárez Garcia 2/7/2023	Followers	541	-	14	2.59%	18	0	1	-	6.1%
Phase 3 Key Achievements 3.2 Posted by Andrea Suárez Garcia 2/6/2023	Followers	122	-	4	3.28%	5	0	1	-	8.2%
IEEE ICC Posted by Andrea Suárez Garcia 2/3/2023	Followers	104	-	3	2.88%	5	0	0	-	7.69%
Open Call for 3rd Party #5G Experimenters STAY TUNED #SGIANA... Posted by Andrea Suárez Garcia 2/2/2023	Followers	342	-	16	4.68%	34	0	7	-	16.67%
Newsflash January 2023 Posted by Andrea Suárez Garcia 2/1/2023	Followers	215	-	6	2.79%	7	0	0	-	6.05%

<p>Presentación de PowerPoint</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>1/30/2023</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	217	-	11	5.07%	11	0	1	-	10.6%
<p>Use Cases</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>1/25/2023</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	347	-	10	2.88%	18	0	1	-	8.36%
<p>#5GIANA was at #5GPPP SME WG meeting yesterday, presenting our upcoming "Ope...</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>1/17/2023</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	509	-	30	5.89%	18	0	1	-	9.63%
<p>Want to follow up on #5GIANA's progress? Then click here https://lnkd.in/d_jyqvB...</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>1/13/2023</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	265	-	9	3.4%	6	0	0	-	5.66%
<p>5G-IANA contribution to ISO standardisation work</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>1/4/2023</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	302	-	11	3.64%	5	0	0	-	5.3%

Figure 14, 5G-IANA LinkedIn most recent posts analysis 1

<p>🎊 Season's Greetings 🎊 from #5GIANA project and best wishes 🎊 for 2023!</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>12/22/2022</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	338	-	10	2.96%	11	0	0	-	6.21%
<p>5G-PPP Reference Figure 2023</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>12/22/2022</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	317	-	26	8.2%	11	0	2	-	12.3%
<p>5G- IANA first webinar</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>12/16/2022</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	350	-	12	3.43%	18	0	2	-	9.14%
<p>HOME</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>12/15/2022</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	177	-	5	2.82%	3	0	0	-	4.52%
<p>Congratulations to our partner INTERNET INSTITUTE Ltd for this extraordinary...</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>12/7/2022</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	230	-	5	2.17%	12	0	0	-	7.39%
<p>5G- IANA presented at the IEEE CSCN 2022</p> <p>Posted by Andrea Suárez García</p> <p>12/2/2022</p> <p>Boost</p>	lowers	289	-	6	2.08%	12	0	2	-	6.92%

Figure 15, 5G-IANA LinkedIn most recent posts analysis 2

2.3.2. Twitter

The [5G-IANA Twitter](#) account is available since M01 of the project. Twitter is one of the most prominent social media platforms in the world, and it is being used to promote 5G-IANA activities to the general public. The hashtag #5GIANA is being used to promote the activities of the project on this social media platform.

Figure 16 presents the activity of the project on this social media platform by analysing the number of tweets and #5GIANA hashtags issued. The figures demonstrate the project is being constantly very active in the promotion and dissemination of activities through this communication tool: 187 hashtags have been promoted until M20 and, on average, the project has posted 4 entries per month.

Figure 16, 5G-IANA tweets & #5GIANA hashtags

Figure 17 provides the number of 5G-IANA Twitter followers: 68 members up to M20. Again, the number of followers coming out of the Consortium is higher (23 followers are Consortium members while 45 are not Consortium members).

Figure 17, 5G-IANA Twitter followers

2.3.3. YouTube Channel

The project's [YouTube channel](#) (Figure 18) was established in M10 and the first, introductory video of the project was created in M17 and [launched in the European Commission stand at the TRA 2022 Conference in Lisbon, Portugal](#). The number of subscribers to this channel is still very low (3 subscribers). However, this is reasonable considering that only 1 of the 10 videos planned throughout the project have been issued and the figure is expected to increase during the second half of the project.

Figure 18, 5G-IANA YouTube channel main page

2.4. Newsletter

The 5G-IANA [Newsletter](#) (Figure 19) aims to raise interest and inform, in a synthesised way, about the project's activities, advancements, upcoming and past events.

INSIDE THIS ISSUE

1. Summary
2. New in 5G-IANA
3. Communication & Dissemination
4. Deliverables
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5G-IANA: a Horizon 2020 project on 5G Intelligent Automotive Network Applications aiming at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services.

The third issue of 5G-IANA Newsletter summarises 5G-IANA's activities from August to November 2022.

This issue puts the focus on the communication and dissemination activities addressed during this five-month period, including our participation in Workshops and Special Sessions, Paper and Project presentations; the launch of the project's Zenodo Community; the first update of the project's website; the launch of the project's first official video!

Following the project's interim review (June 2022), 5G-IANA is on a fast track towards developing and releasing the first release of the Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP). During the past four months, the design of the AOEP platform has progressed in detail, with the objective of opening up and exposing proper interfaces to experimenters of automotive-based applications in the 5G ecosystem. Moreover, useful Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined for the purposes of evaluation and analysis not only of the 5G-IANA Use Cases but also of third-party services and NetApps of potential experimenters on the AOEP.

Figure 19, 5G-IANA Newsletter issue 3 front page

Originally planned to be published every six months (the first 5G-IANA Newsletter was issued in January 2022 and the second one in July 2022) now it is being published four times a year. The third issue was published in November 2022 and the fourth one is planned for March 2023 (as a special edition about the launch of the 5G-IANA first Open Call). In total, the project plans to issue 9 Newsletters (Table 1, 5G-IANA Newsletter issues).

Table 1, 5G-IANA Newsletter issues

5G-IANA Newsletter issues
5G-IANA Newsletter #1 - January 2022
5G-IANA Newsletter #2 - July 2022
5G-IANA Newsletter #3 - November 2022
5G-IANA Newsletter #4 - March 2023
5G-IANA Newsletter #5 - July 2023
5G-IANA Newsletter #6 - November 2023
5G-IANA Newsletter #7 - March 2024
5G-IANA Newsletter #8 - July 2024
5G-IANA Newsletter #9 - November 2024

Newsletters are uploaded to the project’s [Zenodo Community](#), published on the website, and distributed via email among subscribers and Consortium members. All issues are in parallel promoted on the project’s social media.

Although the number of subscribers is still low (13), T7.1 is also tracking the number of downloads in Zenodo. Those figures (Newsletter#1 had 24 downloads, Newsletter#2 17 downloads and Newsletter#3 13 downloads) show a real interest on the information provided through this channel. Nevertheless, the following mitigation measures to improve the performance of this tool are being implemented:

- update the option to subscribe (Figure 20) on the website homepage in order to make it more visible and accessible to web users.
- execute more specific social media campaigns to promote the Newsletter.

Subscribe to 5G-IANA Newsletter

Subscribe to our mailing list to receive 5G-IANA news, updates and events directly in your inbox.

Mail Address *

Privacy policy *

I hereby confirm that I want to sign up for the 5G-IANA newsletter. I also accept that my data may be used for any communication related to the the project.

SUBSCRIBE

Figure 20, Option to subscribe to 5G-IANA newsletter on website home page

2.5. Printed and digital communication materials

The first version of the printed communication materials was issued during this period. The design of these materials was conceived in printed and digital format so they can be used in printed version at events and digitally to support any project needs in communication and dissemination.

These materials have contributed to support the objective of informing target stakeholders about the project's main objectives and expected outcomes and results and have been already used at project events. The poster was part of the project's presentation at the [Vehicle and Transportation Technology Innovation Meetings \(VTM\)](#) in Torino in March 2022 (Figure 21). The poster and the roll-up banner supported 5G-IANA [project booth at the CINEA Connecting Europe Days](#) held on June 2022 in Lyon (Figure 22). Project flyers were also distributed at both events. The roll-banner has also been used during project meetings (Figure 23).

Figure 21, 5G-IANA presentation at the VTM Torino 2022

Figure 22, project booth at the CINEA Connecting Europe Days 2022

Figure 23, 5G-IANA roll-up banner at a project meeting

At present, the Communication Management is also working on a new version of the poster, as well as on a new version of the brochure/factsheet that will focus on the project's Open Call, in order to attract third-party experimenters.

2.5.1. Flyer

The [flyer](#) (Figure 24) was designed in M8, in a simple double page A5, presenting the main high-level objectives of the project and two maps with the testbed sites and consortium partners; it also includes the project's general information and contact information.

Figure 24, 5G-IANA first version of the flyer

2.5.2. Poster

The first version of the [poster](#) (Figure 25) was issued in M12 in a Standard A0 size, to serve as a complementary communication tool at project booths, workshops, presentations, or demonstration events. It also presents the main high-level objectives of

the project, the 5G-IANA consortium partners, as well as project general information and contact information.

Figure 25, 5G-IANA first version of the poster

2.5.3. Brochure

The brochure (Figure 26) was published in M18. Together with the intro and objectives of the project, general and contact information, and the Consortium details, it provides an overview of the testbeds and Use Cases as well as summary of the expected benefits of the project.

Figure 26, 5G-IANA first version of the brochure

2.5.4. Digital banners for the promotion of events

A digital banner (Figure 27) has been created for the promotion of the project during online events, such as webinars, workshops, presentations, etc.

Figure 27, digital banner for promoting events

2.5.5. Roll-up banner

The [roll-up banner](#) (Figure 28) was also designed in M12 to be used as a complementary communication tool during internal meetings and external events.

Figure 28, 5G-IANA roll-up banner

2.5.6. Digital material specifically developed for Open Call #1

Digital materials have been specifically designed and created to support the promotional and communication activities of the first 5G-IANA Open Call.

2.5.6.1. Digital banners

Digital banners templates (Figure 29) have been created to support announcements during the promotional social media campaigns. Another banner template (Figure 30) has been created to support the promotion of webinars to be organised during the first Open Call.

Figure 29, Example of 5G-IANA Open Call #1 social media banner (“Save the Date”)

Figure 30, Digital banner for the promotion of the Open Call Info Day webinar

2.5.6.2. Digital Flyer

A digital flyer (Figure 31) has been also created to support the announcement and promotion of key moments or activities during the Open Call (the Info Day, application period, winners and results, etc.) both on the website and social media.

Figure 31, Example of 5G-IANA Open Call #1 digital flyer

2.5.6.3. Guide for Applicants

The “[Guide for Applicants](#)” (Figure 32) has been created by the project in order to summarize the conditions and procedures of the first Open Call. T7.1 has worked on the edition of this guide with a professional design so as to make it more attractive for the reader.

Figure 32, 5G-IANA Open Call #1 Guide for Applicants cover

2.6. Press releases and conferences

Press releases are published by the consortium at key moments of the project, aiming to communicate important information to target audiences and announcing significant achievements and major upcoming events.

A press release template in English is created by the WP7 lead in collaboration with the Project Coordinator and published on the [project's website](#). This template is distributed among the partners in order to adapt it to their local contexts and to translate it into their mother tongues for dissemination to the local media. Partners are also encouraged to share press releases in their available channels in order to increase the project's achievements and awareness.

The first press release announcing the launch of the project and the kick-off meeting held in Athens was published on the [project's website](#) (Figure 33).

PRESS RELEASE

30 November 2021
info@5g-iana.

The EU project 5G-IANA kicks off to accelerate the creation and commercialisation of 5G-based Automotive Applications

- The project gathers 16 partners from 8 European countries
- An Open 5G Intelligent Experimentation Platform will be developed and available for companies in the sector
- The disruptive approach of the project intends to exploit obtained results through 7 different use cases

5G-IANA is an EU-funded project focused on providing agents of the automotive and mobility sectors with an open 5G intelligent experimentation platform. This platform will enable companies (especially SMEs) to develop, implement and test their automotive services as well as to accelerate their development prior to the commercialization phase.

The AOEP (Automotive Open Experimental Platform) platform, which lies in the core of 5G-IANA, will consist of a complete set of hardware and software resources that will make up an advanced communications IT infrastructure applied to transport, taking advantage of 5G intelligent networks' potential. It will be coupled with an enhanced NetApp Toolkit tailored to the mobility sector, available to all companies and agents of the service value chain. 5G-IANA will put at the disposal of these users secured and standardized APIs for accelerating the production stage of new services.

Within the framework of this project, different virtualization technologies will be investigated and developed for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, MEC nodes and cloud resources).

Statement from the project coordinator:

'5G-IANA aims at boosting 5G uptake on key segments of the automotive industry, where 5G/B5G business practical applications carry tremendous potential. The project is designed to bring significant changes in the automotive sector, impacting society at large, by delivering 5G solutions that are set to tackle challenges associated with road safety and energy efficiency, while also creating new business opportunities for SMEs and Start-Ups.' mentions project coordinator Dr. Angelos Amditis from ICCS/I-Sense Group.

5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven automotive-related use cases in two 5G testbeds: one operated by NOKIA in Ulm, Germany, and one operated by Telekom Slovenia in Ljubljana, Slovenia. Validation scenarios will be the following: remote driving; manoeuvres coordination for autonomous driving; virtual bus tour; Augmented Reality (AR) content delivery for vehicular networks; parking circulation and high-risk driving hotspot detection; network status monitoring; and situational awareness in cross border road tunnel accidents.

Figure 33, 5G-IANA first press release

The press release was also distributed by several partners through their own channels (Table 2):

Table 2, 5G-IANA first press release by partners

Press Release #1
Project's website
VICOM website
UBI website
HIT website
5COMM website

The [second press release](#) of the project (Figure 34) was issued in February 2023 announcing the project's first Open Call:

PRESS RELEASE

23 February 2023
info@5g-iana.

Open Call for SMEs in the automotive vertical sector | 5G-IANA

The project organises an Open Call for the involvement and engagement of "third parties" with the 5G-IANA "Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP)".

5G-IANA project

5G-IANA started in June 2021 and is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016427. The project aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive vertical sector will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced Networked Application (nApp) Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector, for simplifying the design and onboarding of new nApps.

More information about the project is available at <https://www.5g-iana.eu/>.

5G-IANA Open Call #1

5G-IANA project is calling for SMEs and start-ups from Europe to apply to the project's first Open Call that will allow them to run their automotive network applications on top of the platform provided by the 5G-IANA project making use of 5G connectivity. The 5G-IANA consortium will support its participants to develop and integrate their innovative idea using the 5G-IANA platform, facilitating in parallel the developed Repository of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs).

The program starts in June 2023 and ends in October 2023. Applications are already open!

- Application period: 22nd February-22nd May 2023
- Evaluation period: 22nd May-31st May 2023
- Pre-testing phase: June-July 2023
- Validation & testing phase: July-October 2023
- Reporting period: November 2023
- Award phase: December 2023

Who can participate?

The call is open to SMEs and start-ups working with the concept of Network Applications (nApps) in the automotive vertical, and which are already developing or are willing to develop a product or service or functionality that leverages 5G capabilities through the 5G-IANA platform. SMEs and start-

Figure 34, 5G-IANA second press release

During the second half of the project, press releases will be systematically used for the announcement, promotion, and follow-up of the Open Call processes. Also, press releases will be issued for the promotion of the demo and the Final event. Press conferences will be as well organised at these events to ensure maximum stakeholder engagement

2.7. Videos

5G-IANA will produce ten videos in total: three project-related videos and at least one short video per UC, showcasing and describing each use case demonstrated during the events.

The [first introductory video](#) of the project (Figure 35) was created in M17 and it was [launched in the European Commission stand at the TRA 2022 Conference in Lisbon](#),

[Portugal](#). The video is animated and offers a short introduction to the project and its goals.

Figure 35, 5G-IANA first introductory video

The second video is planned for M30 in parallel with the promotion of the project’s second Open Call, providing a “how-to-experiment tutorial” to the selected SMEs and third-party experimenters and a hands-on showcase of the platform capabilities, together with some practical nApp examples. The third video will be produced towards the end of the project (M40), summarizing the project’s outcomes and including a compilation of the project’s 7 use case videos which will be produced during the two (public) demo events.

The videos will be disseminated via the project’s social media and website, and will be available for promotion at fairs, conferences or other relevant events and upon request.

2.8. Zenodo Community

The [5G-IANA Zenodo Community](#) (Figure 36) has been created in M14 of the project. The scope of this community is to make freely available and under open access status all public deliverables, scientific publications and publicly available results of the 5G-IANA H2020 Project.

5G-IANA H2020 Project

Recent uploads

November 29, 2022 (v1)
Other
Open Access
View

5G-IANA #3 Newsletter - November 2022
 Andrea Suárez,
 The third 5G-IANA's Newsletter published in November 2022.
 Uploaded on January 31, 2023

January 16, 2023 (v1)
Presentation
Open Access
View

Open Call opportunity for SMEs in the automotive sector
 Eirini Liotou,
 Presentation addressed by 5G-IANA project Deputy Coordinator to the members of the 5G-PPP SME Working Group, on 16th January 2023, about the 5G-IANA Open Call, an opportunity for SMEs in the automotive sector.
 Uploaded on January 30, 2023

October 14, 2022 (v1)
Preprint
Open Access
View

The 5G-IANA platform: Bringing far-edge resources and ML potential to the disposal of automotive third parties
● Francesca Moscatelli, ● Thanos Xirofotis, ● Amr Rizk, ● Nehal Baganal-Krishna, ● Edoardo Bonetto, ● Eirini Liotou, ● Angelos Amditis,
 The advent of 5G has been a game-changer in the Automotive Vertical sector. 5G acts as an enabler of advanced networking architectures which, in turn, allow the development of novel services, by attracting and engaging third parties to experiment using available 5G infrastructure and connectivity. 5
 Uploaded on November 9, 2022

October 18, 2022 (v1)
Project deliverable
Open Access
View

5G-IANA - D7.6 Dissemination Plan
 Sevi Christoforou,
 [Deliverable pending final approval by the EC] D7.6 Dissemination Plan defines the dissemination strategy and the plan of action that will be implemented by the 5G-IANA consortium to ensure that the project and its results are effectively communicated throughout the project's lifecycle. I
 Uploaded on November 8, 2022
1 more version(s) exist for this record

October 19, 2022 (v1)
Project deliverable
Open Access
View

5G-IANA - D5.1 - Initial validation KPIs and metrics
 Alexis Aivaliotis, Claudio Russo, David Alemany Ibor, ● Dimitrios Klonidis, ● Fotis Foukalas, ● Francesca Moscatelli, ● Francois Fischer, ● Jörg Schapperle, ● Konstantinos Katsaros, ● Manuel Fuentes, ● Marios Zinonos, ● Markus Wimmer, ● Matteo Andolfi, ● Miriam Ortiz Monet, ● Nehal Baganal-Krishna, ● Pasquale Marasco, ● Peter Schmitting, ● Rudolf Sušnik, ● Thanos Xirofotis, ● Yann Garcia,
 [Deliverable pending final approval by the EC] The present document is deliverable D5.1 'Initial validation KPIs and metrics' of the 5G-IANA project. The main objective of the deliverable is to provide an initial set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and metrics for evaluation an
 Uploaded on November 8, 2022

New upload

Community

5G-IANA H2020 Project

The **EU project 5G-IANA** is an ICT-41 Horizon 2020 project that aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the **Automotive-related 5G-PPP** vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An **Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP)** will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced **NetApp Toolkit** tailored to the Automotive sector.

5G-IANA aims to increase the uptake of 5G starting from the key Automotive industrial segment, where 5G/B5G business practical applications carry tremendous potential. The project is also working towards increasing road safety, improving traffic flow by increasing road utilisation and promoting an interactive and enhanced travel experience for drivers and passengers.

This community includes all **public deliverables, scientific publications, and publicly available results of the 5G-IANA H2020 Project**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427

Project's website: <https://www.5g-iana.eu/>

Curated by:
sevichristoforou

Duration policy:
Not specified

Created:
July 11, 2022

Harvesting API:
[OAI-PMH Interface](#)

Figure 36, 5G-IANA Zenodo Community main page

2.9. Webinars

Webinars addressing different topics and categories of stakeholders will be organised at regular intervals to provide a comprehensive view of particular results of the project and share key messages and useful information with third-party experimenters. 5G-IANA will organise 9 webinars in total.

A [first \(internal\) webinar](#) has been already organised in M18 and conducted by the project's Technical Coordinator (UBI). A dedicated webinar campaign is foreseen during the application period of the first Open Call as a way of attracting the attention of

experimenters to the use of the 5G-IANA platform. More specifically, an “Info Day” is planned for M22 where the 5G-IANA AOEP Release 1 offerings and nApps will be presented together with the logistics and administrative procedures for applying to the Open Call. Additionally, a webinar will be organised for the official presentation of the 5G-IANA test sites. Another webinar is foreseen during the main phase of the Open Call (pre-testing and validation) with the aim of presenting practical examples of on nApps for the automotive sector, based on the 5G-IANA use cases.

The detailed plan of 5G-IANA webinars until the end of the project is available in the revised version of D7.6 – Dissemination Plan.

3. IMPACT EVALUATION UNTIL M20 (KPIs)

This section refers to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the impact achieved by 5G-IANA communication tools and activities during this period (M1-M20).

Table 3 presents the communication activities and related KPIs together with the achievements made.

Table 3, 5G-IANA communication activities and impact M1-M20

Communication activity	KPI target value				M1-M20 achievements
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3-end*	Total	
Website: Total visits per month	100	160	300	>300	163 (average/month)
Twitter: 5G-IANA hashtags	80	160	250	300	187
LinkedIn: Members of 5G-IANA Group (out of Consortium members)	65	130	260	>300	163
Video: number produced	-	>2	>8	10	1
Project brochure: number produced	1	Update	Update	3	1
Technical leaflets: published and distributed	>100	>100	>100	300	200
Press releases: number issued	1	2	6	9	2
Newsletters: number of reads ¹	50	100	150	200	67

* The third column includes all the produced results (performance) until the completion of 5G-IANA lifecycle, including the project's extension, i.e., M25 - M42.

¹ This indicator is based on the number of subscribers plus the number of downloads of Newsletters in Zenodo.

4. CONCLUSION

In this deliverable the communications tools, channels and resources defined to execute the project's communication activities have been presented in detail: the document summarises the activity performed with the tools put in place and introduces the updates and improvements adopted to better align with the third-party engagement plan defined and the overall needs of the project. The document has also presented the impact achieved by the communication activities and tools up to M20. Upcoming plans and mitigation measures have been also indicated when needed.

The final impact achieved by the communication tools and channels is expected to be reported at the end of the project under D7.8 – Report on the dissemination activities (M42)².

² The project plans to report the communication activities and the impact achieved by the communication tools and channels at the end of the project together with the final dissemination activities report.